
Pragmatic approach to determiners in diplomatic language

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Abstract: As a natural phenomenon, determiners exist widely in various fields. Naturally, there are a lot of determiners in diplomatic language. Diplomacy is the exchange of affairs between sovereign states, and language, as the main carrier of foreign affairs activities, naturally plays an indispensable role. Diplomacy covers a wide range, and the "diplomacy" in this study is only limited to political diplomacy. This study mainly focuses on the pragmatic types and relevant methods of determiners in diplomatic language, which discusses in diplomatic occasions, especially political and diplomatic occasions, how a diplomat use determiners flexibly and what kind of strategies should be adopted to circumvent the embarrassment caused by such language skill as the emergence of certain determiners, rendering flexibility and precision of determiner prominent. Therefore, a competent and qualified diplomat should make overall plan and take all factors into consideration, so as to promote the harmonious practice. This study in some sense broadens the field of determines. It is hoped that this study can provide some inspiration for the pragmatic study of determiners in diplomatic language and help people understand the deep meaning behind determiner and diplomatic language.

Key words: determiner; diplomatic language; pragmatic analysis

I. Introduction

It is the essence of diplomacy to adjust international political relations through negotiation. Consequently, language, as a tool to bridge different cultures, must be used accurately and skillfully so as to foster the harmonious communication and smooth deal. There is no denying that emphasis has been placed on such kind of language as formal, polite and euphemistic equivalents. In diplomatic language, the flexible use of language strategies is not only out of the need for politeness, but also out of the need for conversation.

It is the fundamental interests that urge diplomats to sit down around the table. Therefore, conflicts and contradictions arising from their pursuit of gains are inevitable, which is the very reason for the existence of diplomacy. As an important carrier of diplomacy, the use of diplomatic language must be cautious.

In diplomatic language, determiners can be selected as words that limit the range, quantity and object by the questioner and respondent, can improve the efficiency of language expression, increase the flexibility of language expression, make the language more euphemistic, implicit, and polite. Using determiner flexibly often have positive effects in answering sensitive questions and moderating the atmosphere of communication.

The purpose of this study is to analyze whether there are special classifications of determiners in diplomatic speech by taking Chinese diplomatic speech as corpus. What is the appropriate way to classify them? Is there a pragmatic approach to determiners in diplomatic speech? If it exists, what strategic principles does it follow?

On the theoretical level of pragmatics, the study of determiner can enrich the pragmatic functions of determiners. By analyzing the pragmatic functions and pragmatic strategies of determiners, we can help people better understand the surface meaning and the deep meaning of diplomatic rhetoric. In this way, the communication and dialogue between different language research fields are enhanced.

II. Literature Reviews

With the advancement of globalization, the exchanges between countries have become more and more frequent, and diplomacy has become inevitable and significant for various countries. In diplomatic occasions, the language used by speakers is often strategic and flexible. A case in point is the frequent use of determiner, which has come a long way.

As the exchanges between countries in the world have become more frequent, diplomatic negotiations often involve major issues in politics, economy, and military affairs. Therefore, diplomats must use a set of euphemisms to express their views in order to safeguard the position and interests of their respective countries, as well as the face of countries on conflict of interests in the process of negotiation. That is which we call diplomatic language. Sir Harold Nicolson (1988) talks about three meanings of diplomatic language in his book *Diplomacy*: The expression “diplomatic language” is used to denote three different things. In its first sense it signifies the actual language (whether it be Latin, French, or English) which is employed by diplomatists in their converse or correspondence with each other. In its second sense it means those technical phrases which, in the course of centuries, have become part of ordinary diplomatic vocabulary. And in its third, and most common sense, it is used to describe that guarded understatement which enables diplomatists and ministers to say sharp things to each other without becoming provocative or impolite.” The third point is the definition of what we called diplomatic language. In this article, diplomatic language’s definition is: in a diplomatic occasion, when a reporter’s question involves some sensitive or sharp questions that are difficult to answer, the diplomat or diplomatic spokesperson or the national leader uses a set of euphemistic, polite and decent wording. The wording is used to achieve the pragmatic purpose of breaking the deadlock, achieve the pragmatic purpose of indicating position, and protecting oneself.

As a new lexical category in modern English grammar, determiners can be found as early as in *A Grammar of Spoken English* by Plamer and Bland Ford (1924). In the 1930s, Bloomfield (2002), the founder of the structuralism language school, called determiners as a branch of adjectives in his famous book *Language*, which points out those determiners are usually placed in front of modifier adjectives. Rando Quirk (1985), a noted contemporary philologist, has argued that qualifier determiner is a separate word class. He also investigates the positions of determiners in various noun phrases and further divides them into three categories: pre-determiners, central determiners and post-determiners. HuKaibao (2006) did not stick to the classification of determiners in traditional semantics. He analyzed the types and translation of cultural determiners in detail from the perspective of culture through domestication and foreignization. Hu Yijun (2011) abandoned the traditional research on semantic determiners and introduced them into the perspective of pragmatic functions to explain their marking functions in context.

Most of the studies on diplomatic language focus on the special linguistic forms of the language itself or on the special contexts covered by the language itself. Scholars tend to be more willing to discuss the existing communicative principles. Little attention has been paid to the use of a particular class of words in diplomatic discourse. The study of determiners is a process of slow and deep development. Due to its special definition of scope, quantity, object and meaning, determiner has been found by scholars to be a new research perspective beyond traditional semantics and grammar. Whether it is the classification of determiners themselves, which allows scholars to discuss from a cultural perspective, or the function of determiners themselves, which allows other scholars to study from a pragmatic perspective, it shows that there are still many gaps in the study of determiners to be explored. Using diplomatic language as a corpus to explore the pragmatic functions of determiners can not only reveal the flexibility and strategy of determiners in the special language form of diplomatic rhetoric, but also help us understand the deep meaning behind diplomatic rhetoric.

III. Types of Determiners in Diplomatic Language

In diplomatic language, we can find that determiners vary to some extent according to the rhetoric employed by the speaker. In this part of this paper, the types of determiners will be described in detail from such four aspects as pun, exaggeration metaphor and irony with cases.

2.1 Pun

The intended linguistic meaning of pun refers to the pragmatic meaning constructed by it, that is, the use of the homonym or polysemy of the words in a certain language situation. It intentionally makes the statement have a double meaning, and the words are intended to be meaningful, and the meaning of the puns is harmonious. The pun can make the language expressive and humorous, and it can impress people and deepen the meaning.

Example 1: The first press conference after the Spring Festival in 2006.

Q: Regarding the resolution of the International Atomic Energy Agency on the Iranian nuclear issue, five countries abstained. China finally voted in favor instead of abstaining from voting. What are the considerations behind it?

Kong Quan: We have the same considerations in the back and in the front. There is nothing secret about it.

The "behind" in this case can be used for two kinds of understandings, one is the specific meaning "back", and the other is the abstract meaning "improper face, darkness". Here, journalists actually ask questions about its abstract meaning, but the spokesperson replaces the abstract meaning with the specific meaning of "back" as "improper face, secretly" is to use the rhetorical means of meaning puns to convey the pragmatic meaning to the recipient.

Example 2: The foreign ministry regular press conference in 1995

Q: Today is Deng Xiaoping's 91st birthday. Has the new saying about his health changed?

Chen Jian: Of course, there was. He was a year older.

In this case, journalists actually ask questions about "Deng Xiaoping's health", asked questions about its specific meaning. Chen Jian use a more specific point of his health—age, that is used to hide the real health of Deng Xiaoping.

In the diplomatic scene, especially in the diplomatic press conference, because the spokespersons use in official language. And he is facing reporters from all over the world, the language is not available, so the voice pun is rarely used.

2.2 Exaggeration

The exaggerated class determiner pragmatic meaning refers to the pragmatic meaning constructed by exaggerating this rhetorical form. Exaggeration refers to the rhetoric of deliberately exaggerating the description of an objective person or thing. Exaggeration has the potential to expand exaggeration, reduce exaggeration, and advance exaggeration. Deliberately turning the general things into a big place is to expand the exaggeration; deliberately turning the general things into small places is to reduce the exaggeration; deliberately to say what happened later is first appearing, or at the same time is the exaggeration. It is more common to expand exaggeration in diplomatic rhetoric.

Example 3:

Q: Recently, China has laid down the US-type U-2 high-altitude reconnaissance plane. What weapons are used? Is it a missile?

Chen Yi: Mr. Reporter, we took it down with bamboo poles!

Example 4: On the morning of February 21, 1972, the US presidential plane landed at the Beijing airport. Nixon, who stepped down the ramp, took the initiative to reach out to meet Premier Zhou Enlai of the State Council of the People's Republic of China.

Premier Zhou said a long history: "Mr. President, you have stretched out the world's vastest ocean to shake hands with me - no connection for 25 years."

In the previous example, from the answer of Minister Chen Yi, the recipient can deduce such pragmatic meaning: the question you asked involves national defense secrets, and it is impossible for me to disclose the state secrets to you; but it is proved our country has a certain air defense capability. In the latter case, we know that this transoceanic handshake shocked the world, marking the "thaw" of Sino-US relations, and the world pattern has changed. Here, "Mr. President, you have stretched out the world's widest ocean to shake hands with me." Using exaggerated methods to express vividly, "The United States and China have a close relationship with peace and development. I hope that both sides will cherish this. This is a historic moment for peace and development of the world."

2.3 Metaphor

The metaphorical class defines pragmatic meaning as the pragmatic meaning constructed by metaphor. The metaphor is also called "metaphor". It is a rhetoric that describes the truth or describes things with things that are different in nature and have similarities. The metaphor can make the profound truths obvious and help people deepen their experience; it can make the generalized things visual and give people a vivid image. The metaphor has the distinction of metaphor, metaphor, and simile. In diplomatic situations, metaphors and metaphors are often used.

Example 5:

Q: It is reported that some Chinese companies have purchased and leased land for agricultural production in Central Asian countries such as Tajikistan in recent years. What is China's response to this?

A: The relevant Chinese departments have made clarifications on this occasion. China does not have the "Overseas Putian" plan. The agricultural cooperation carried out by the Chinese side is based on mutual voluntariness, equality, and mutual benefit. As a friendly neighbor of the Central Asian countries, China is willing to conduct friendly and mutually beneficial cooperation in various fields with relevant countries on the principle of mutual respect, mutual benefit and win-win.

The metaphor means that the ontology does not appear, or does not appear in this sentence, but instead borrows the metaphor instead of the ontology. In this case, the spokesperson directly used the metaphor "Overseas Putian" to replace the "Chinese company buys and leases land in agricultural production in Central Asian countries such as Tajikistan", which visualizes the generalized things and gives them a clear picture. image of.

Example 6: On February 17, 2011, Foreign Ministry Spokesperson Ma Zhaoxu held a regular press conference.

Q: It is reported that China will provide two giant pandas to the Tokyo Zoo for collaborative research next week. Some analysis said that this will improve the feelings of the Japanese and Chinese people. What expectations does China have for this project?

A: I don't know the exact time when the giant panda will go to Tokyo. But I agree with you that the friendly feelings between China and Japan, especially the two peoples, should be further strengthened. China will continue to make efforts to this end. I also hope that the giant panda will act as a friendly messenger of the Chinese and Japanese peoples and play a role in enhancing the friendly feelings and mutual understanding between the two peoples.

Example 7: Zhou Enlai's conversation with the Soviet ambassador.

Ambassador of the Soviet Union: "Comrade Prime Minister, I heard that there has been an earth-shattering event in China recently?"

Zhou Enlai: "There is nothing big, it is just a tree in the forest; a leaf falls on a tree."

The Soviet ambassador: "According to the authority, the impact of this matter on China is extremely unfavorable!"

Zhou Enlai: "On the contrary, a tumor disappears automatically on the body, and there is no harm."

Ambassador of the Soviet Union: "Comrade Prime Minister, I have long wanted to say something. You have been vocal in the international arena that we are social imperialism and we are stigmatized more than the toilet. This is the case, then: Your Deputy Commander Lin is Why should we go to our Soviet Union under one person and 10,000 people in China?"

Zhou Enlai: "Because the toilet is stinky, the flies love the place. Since the comrades understand this truth, why bother to ask?"

Metaphor is also called "metaphor". Both ontology and metaphor appear in sentences, using metaphors such as "as", "yes", "become", "become", and "equal". In the case of the sensitive issue of Sino-Japanese relations, the spokesperson in Example 7 directly compared the giant panda to the friendly messenger of the Chinese and Japanese peoples and revealed that "China is a country that loves peace. China sincerely hopes to develop friendly relations with Japan." "The pragmatic meaning of this. In the case of the 7th, the Prime Minister of the Republic of China compared Lin Biao to "a tree", "a leaf" and "a cancer", indicating that the so-called big event of the Soviet ambassador is not worth mentioning; but comparing Lin Biao to "fly", the Soviet Union likes "The toilet has highlighted the corruption of the Soviet socialist atmosphere.

2.4 Irony

The anti-linguistic determiner meaning refers to the pragmatic meaning constructed by the rhetoric. The irony is also called "reverse" and "opposite". It refers to a kind of rhetoric that intentionally uses words or sentences that are contrary to the original meaning to express the meaning.

Example 8: Li Ruihuan visits Hong Kong

Q: In your speech, you stressed the importance of unity. Does that mean Hong Kong people are not united enough?

Li Ruihuan: Then I wish you good health now. Does that mean you're not healthy?

Example 9: On February 17, 2011, Foreign Ministry Spokesperson Ma Zhaoxu held a regular press conference.

Q: The Canadian side said that the website of the Canadian government department was attacked by a "hacker" from China. What's your opinion?

A: I would like to point out that the Chinese government attaches great importance to computer network security and manages the Internet according to law. The Chinese government has consistently and resolutely opposed any criminal activities that undermine the Internet and computer network systems, including "hacking", and crack down on it according to law. Regarding the specific questions you mentioned, I don't know if there is any basis. The so-called Chinese government's support for "hacker" attacks is purely out of thin air and has ulterior motives.

In diplomatic situations, the appropriate use of irony by the spokesperson to define such a rhetoric can make speech more combative and sometimes even more powerful than positive arguments. Irony can be used in satire, criticism, disclosure, etc., and can also be used in humor and so on. In the first case, "unity" and "health" mean the opposite in the speaker's mouth. The second spokesperson also used the rhetoric of the irony, deliberately using words or sentences that are contrary to the original meaning to express the original intention, and profoundly pointed out that the so-called Chinese government's support for "hacker" attacks has ulterior motives and is purely out of nothing.

1. Pragmatic analysis of determiners in diplomatic language

In diplomatic occasions, as speakers often face some sharp remarks or sensitive issues, they often adopt some strategies in language. Through research, this paper finds that speakers also follow some pragmatic strategies when using determiner.

3.1 Logical significance of determiners in diplomatic language

3.1.1 Shifted focus

The focus transfer class defines pragmatic meaning as the pragmatic meaning constructed by the transfer of each focus in the discourse. The speaker is speaking about an event in the vocabulary, but actually highlighting another event. As we all know, in the process of people's daily speech communication activities, each sentence will have one or more focus. In most cases, answering the question is to answer the main focus questions. However, in a diplomatic setting, the spokesperson sometimes does not answer the main focus, but uses the secondary focus as a breakthrough; sometimes avoids all the focus, or proposes a new focus instead of the focus of the reporter, or directly pushes to the first Three parties. In the diplomatic rhetoric, the meaning of the focus shifting pragmatics mainly includes: the meaning of the main form of the sub-character, the pragmatic meaning of the old-fashioned version, the pragmatic meaning of the old-fashioned version, and the pragmatic meaning of the third-party type.

3.1.1.1 The primary focus shifts to the secondary focus

When a questioner asks a question to a speaker, there are usually several focal points in the question. If the primary focus is not appropriate for the answer, the speaker tends to focus the answer on the secondary focus.

Example 10: On June 2, 2011, Foreign Ministry Spokesperson Hong Lei held a regular press conference.

Q: Due to the leakage incident at the Fukushima nuclear power plant in Japan, the German government recently decided to close all nuclear power plants in the future. Does China consider adopting similar measures?

A: Premier Wen Jiabao presided over the relevant meeting of the State Council, emphasizing the full understanding of the importance and urgency of nuclear safety. Nuclear power development should put safety first. We have introduced the relevant decisions of the meeting on this occasion, namely: First, organize a comprehensive security inspection of China's domestic nuclear facilities. Second, earnestly strengthen the safety management of the nuclear facilities that are in operation. Third, comprehensive review of nuclear power plants under construction. Fourth, strict approval of new nuclear power projects. The relevant Chinese departments will speed up the preparation of nuclear safety plans, and adjust and improve the medium and long-term planning of nuclear power development.

In diplomatic situations, spokespersons often choose the secondary focus of the question as a breakthrough to answer questions that are difficult to answer directly. The recipient's discussion of the secondary focus can deduce the pragmatic meaning that the speaker is trying to convey. For example, in the above example, the reporter wants to know if China decides to shut down all nuclear power plants in the future. Faced with this problem, the spokesperson focused on the focus of "nuclear security" in this utterance, deliberately ignoring the main focus, and letting the recipient understand his intention from the secondary focus statement: based on the current stage of China's national conditions, China will not decide to shut down the nuclear power plant.

3.1.2 New Focus Replaces Old Focus

When a questioner asks a question to a speaker, if the question has only one focus and it is not easy to answer, the speaker will often propose a new focus to steal the concept and replace the questioner's question focus.

Example 11:

Q: The United States is deploying military power around Libya and claiming to intervene in the Libyan conflict by force. What is China's position on this? Do you think that the relevant resolutions of the Security Council include military means?

A: China has always been very concerned about the situation in Libya and hopes to restore social stability and normal order as soon as possible. The parties concerned will resolve the current crisis through peaceful means through dialogue. In the process, the security and interests of nationals and institutions in Libya must be ensured.

Example 12: On April 26, 2011, Foreign Ministry Spokesperson Hong Lei held a regular press conference.

Q: The South Korean said that the other five parties to the six-party talks have agreed that the DPRK-ROK dialogue should be held before the resumption of the Six-Party Talks, and that the DPRK should show a

responsible attitude toward the "Cheonan" incident and the "Yanting Island shelling" incident. What is China's comment?

A: Maintaining peace and stability on the peninsula, concerned is in line with the fundamental interests of all parties concerned in the region and is also the fundamental starting point and end point for China to handle the peninsula. Under the current situation, we hope that all parties will show flexibility and active interaction, restart the dialogue and consultation process as soon as possible, and jointly guide the situation to develop in a better direction. China is willing to work with all parties concerned to continue to play a positive and constructive role in achieving peace and stability on the peninsula and in the region.

In the above two examples, the speaker has sought a new focus in the process of answering the question. The recipient can understand the pragmatic meaning of the speaker's intention through this new focus. In Example 11, the spokesperson put forward a new focus in the answer, which is to resolve the current crisis in Libya by peaceful means through dialogue, and to focus on strengthening this focus, without saying that the force exerted by reporters interferes with this focus. He expressed to the recipient that "China has always insisted on not interfering in other countries' internal affairs and advocated peaceful resolution of the Libyan issue through dialogue and condemned the United States that claimed to intervene in the Libyan conflict by force." In Example 12, the spokesperson was speaking in the statement of the "peaceful settlement of disputes through dialogue and consultation", the actual point is to highlight the pragmatic meaning of "the DPRK and the ROK should focus on maintaining peace on the peninsula and should not be preoccupied with some details."

3.1.1.3 The focus converts to the third party

When the questioner asks a question to the speaker, the speaker will often tell the questioner that the question does not belong to the scope of the speaker's answer and business scope in order to avoid the question, so as to refuse to disclose sensitive information.

Example 13: On January 6, 2011, Foreign Ministry Spokesperson Hong Lei held a regular press conference.

Q: We have seen pictures and reports about the "J-20" fighter jet on the Internet. Is China really developing a new generation of fighters?

A: Please understand the specific issue to the military. I want to emphasize that China adheres to the path of peaceful development and pursues a defensive national defense policy, which does not pose a threat to any country.

Example 14: On April 7, 2011, Foreign Ministry Spokesperson Hong Lei held a regular press conference.

Q: The Chinese media disclosed photos of China's first aircraft carrier. Please confirm.

A: Please refer to the competent authorities for details. I want to emphasize that China adheres to the path of peaceful development and pursues a defensive national defense policy, which does not pose a threat to any country.

Example 15: On June 7, 2011, Foreign Ministry Spokesperson Hong Lei held a regular press conference.

Q: China has reportedly built an aircraft carrier and will launch it soon. Will this aircraft carrier be deployed in the Indian Ocean or the south China sea?

A: For details, please contact the competent authorities. I want to point out that China unwaveringly follows the path of peaceful development, implements a defensive national defense policy, and pursues good-neighborly friendship. In recent years, China's military strength has achieved certain development, and the degree of modernization of the military has increased. This improvement is entirely within the reasonable scope of self-defense defense. Compared with developed countries and more developed countries, China's weapons and equipment still have a relatively large gap. China's national defense capability will not pose a threat to any country.

At the regular press conference held by the spokesperson, the reporter sometimes mentioned some information that was beyond the scope of the Ministry of Foreign Affairs or was temporarily difficult to publish. In the face of these problems, spokespersons often directly push the issue to third parties. This aspect is conducive to embodying the responsibility of the spokesperson of the Ministry of Foreign Affairs. From the examples of Examples 13, 14, and 15 cited above, the "special questions asked by the spokesperson should be

known to the military", "Please refer to the competent authorities for details", "For specific information, please The competent authorities understand that "the words are all in the meaning of indicating to the recipient that "such questions are inconvenient to talk about". What deserves our attention here is that after the spokesperson is pushed to a third party, it is often necessary to emphasize some things. The recipients can also understand the rich pragmatic meaning that the speaker tries to convey through these emphasized words.

3.1.4 Extended reference

The pragmatic meaning of the imaginary and imaginary class refers to the pragmatic meaning between the literal meaning and the intra-lingual meaning, which allows the recipient to comprehend in the virtual reality. According to the differences between the literal meaning and the semantic meaning of the words in diplomatic rhetoric and the meaning of the words in language, the pragmatic meaning of the virtual words and the pragmatic meaning of the real words can be expressed. The general meaning of the words refers to the specific meaning of the words and the peculiar meaning of the words. There are two types of limited pragmatic meaning.

It refers to the inconvenience of the presenter to specifically refer to something, and deliberately expand the pragmatic meaning constructed by the discourse extension. For example, in order to get rid of unnecessary troubles and sinless people, the spokesperson tends to use specific words such as "relevant countries", "relevant countries", "other countries" and "related parties" to avoid specific references.

Example 16:

Q: It is reported that China and Vietnam often have some disputes at sea. How will China handle such disputes?

A: China has indisputable sovereignty over the Nansha Islands and its adjacent waters. We have always been committed to properly handling and resolving disputes in the South China Sea through dialogue and negotiation, and working with relevant countries to maintain peace and stability in the South China Sea. On the South China Sea issue, the Chinese government has always adopted a highly concerned and responsible attitude, maintained great restraint, and put forward the idea of "shelving disputes and jointly developing" in a constructive manner. We hope that the relevant disputes can be settled peacefully through bilateral consultations with relevant countries in accordance with recognized international law and modern maritime law, including the basic principles and legal systems established by the United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea.

We hope that countries inside and outside the country will respect and support the efforts of relevant countries to peacefully resolve bilateral disputes through practical actions, promote good-neighborliness, mutual trust, friendly cooperation and regional stability, and will not complicate relevant disputes.

However, the spokesperson did not touch any specific country in the answer, but used the "relevant countries" and "related countries". Some imaginary words such as "countries inside and outside the domain". We know that during this period, China has more than one country controversial on the South China Sea issue, as well as the Philippines, Brunei, Indonesia and other countries. The use of "relevant countries" and "relevant countries" here to avoid direct talks about Vietnam, and also conveyed to the recipients such a pragmatic meaning: not only in Vietnam, but also in the Philippines, Brunei, Indonesia and other countries. On the South China Sea issue, the relevant disputes should be resolved peacefully through bilateral consultations, mutual benefit and win-win results. It is also worth noting that the general term "country inside and outside the country" was used by speaker. I believe that the receiver's understanding of the South China Sea incident should be able to easily conclude that "the country inside and outside the country" is actually referring to Japan and These two countries in the United States.

Example 17: On January 18, 2011, Foreign Ministry Spokesperson Hong Lei held a regular press conference.

Q: Is this arrangement unusual? What information will be passed to the world?

A: During President Hu Jintao's visit, he often met with other heads of state, met with reporters and answer questions from reporters. President Hu's visit to the US is an important one on the occasion of the 40th anniversary of the resumption of China-US relations. We hope that this visit will promote the positive and cooperative development of China-US relations, further determine the direction of China-US relations in the new era and push bilateral relations to a new level.

Example 18: On June 23, 2011, Foreign Ministry Spokesperson Hong Lei held a regular press conference. Q: US President Barack Obama issued a national speech on the 22nd, announcing plans to withdraw from the US military from Afghanistan. What is China's comment? A: We have always advocated respect for the independence and sovereignty of Afghanistan. We have noticed that President Obama announced plans to withdraw troops from Afghanistan. We hope relevant parties will earnestly shoulder their responsibilities in the process of transferring security power to Afghanistan, help Afghanistan to strengthen its security capacity building, and ensure a peaceful and stable transition.

The spokesperson in Example 17 used "other heads of state" to refer to "President Obama" and conveyed to the recipient that "the meeting with President Obama during the visit of President Hu Jintao to the United States and answering questions from reporters" is not unusual and does not exist. It has special significance; the spokesperson in Example 18 uses the false word of "related parties" to avoid direct speaking to the United States. Although the vocabulary is conveying the Chinese's concern about the reconstruction of Afghanistan to the recipient, the actual expression is "The territory and sovereignty of any country are inviolable." If we take into account the history of Afghanistan, we find that "related parties" actually refer not only to the United States, but also to the former Britain and the Soviet Union. In the regular press conference held by the spokesperson, in addition to the "related/related aspects" (department, media, regulations, reports, countries), "minority" (country, media), "these / some / part / some organizations (national, reporting, media) and other imaginary words, also commonly used to some of the words, such as: any, all, everything, etc., covering the object and covering a wide range are the characteristics of covering the object and covering and wide range.

We know that the use of arbitrary words can greatly expand the number of objects referred to, and therefore has strong uncertainty and abstraction. In diplomatic situations, spokespersons often use the infinity of the number of objects to make an article, so that the answer is abstract and uncertain, thus avoiding the many hidden dangers caused by direct and direct answering questions. In Example 20, the term "any country" used by the spokesperson is intended to convey to the recipient the pragmatic meaning of "China is committed to peaceful development and has no intention of threatening the United States"; The pragmatic meaning that the state intends to express to the recipient is: If the United States interferes in China's internal affairs with excuses such as Internet freedom, China is absolutely not allowed. Here, the spokesperson uses "any country" to refer specifically to the "United States", and "the countries of the world" refers to "China" in a generic sense. In the regular press conference held by the spokesperson, there are also some collective words that express the concept of plurals, such as journalists from various countries, us, them, everyone, and so on. Spokespersons use these broad-based extensions to avoid specific references and to maximize the scope of the indication.

Through the analysis of the corpus, we conclude and summarize the words with specific formal meaning, mainly as follows:

False determiners: related/related aspects (regulations, departments, countries, reports, media), some/some/these/what/minor/partial countries (organizations, people, reports, media), etc.;

Any stipulated words: any, all, everything, etc.;

Collective determiners: the international community, national leaders, us, them, everyone, the people, and so on.

3.2 Pragmatic principles followed by determiners in modern diplomatic language

3.2.1 Confidentiality principle

Confidentiality refers to the behavior constraints on personnel engaged in the political, economic, cultural, military and other aspects of the state. All state organs, the armed forces, political parties, public organizations, enterprise, institutions and citizens shall have the duty to keep state secrets. Confidentiality is an important guarantee for the normal and smooth implementation of major state diplomacy, and carry out diplomatic work smoothly.

In diplomatic situations, diplomatic spokespersons or state leaders must stand on the standpoint of the government and national interests when journalists or other diplomats mention some sensitive questions about China's political, economic, and military aspects. Adhere to certain confidentiality principles and use some determiners skillfully so that the communication between the two parties can proceed smoothly.

Example 19: Discussing the cooperation between China and ASEAN in Brunei (November 4-6, 2001) (On the morning of November 5, 2001, after attending the breakfast meeting of leaders of China, Japan and South Korea at the Centre Hotel)

Reporter: Hello Prime Minister. Can you tell us what is the news of the leaders of the two countries in South Korea and Japan this morning? What news?

Zhu Rongji: What news? It's all old news. (Zhu Rongji answered the reporter's question to the editorial team, "Zhu Rongji answered the reporter")

Premier Zhu Rongji's answer to the reporter's question was not the information that the reporter wanted. If he actively answer the reporter's question, he may reveal some national secrets or involve sensitive topics. To some extent, Threatening your face. Under this circumstance, Premier Zhu Rongji ingeniously answered the reporter's question in a question-and-answer manner. In fact, he avoided the reporter's question and directly answered it with the determiner of the old news. This answer both relieved the other party's negative face. The threat also enhances their positive face in order to achieve the purpose of communication.

3.2.2 National Interest Principle

In foreign-related activities, there is a principle that must be observed, that is, in line with the national interests. Any organization or individual must implement it in foreign-related activities. This principle stresses the maintenance of national interests and dignity on the basis of respect for the interests and dignity of other states. "Commonly refers to the country's cultural, diplomatic, security, political and economic interests." In foreign exchanges, the core of safeguarding national interests is to safeguard the sovereign independence, territorial integrity and national dignity of the country.

In diplomatic situations, diplomatic spokespersons or state leaders must always remember that they are not representing individuals but on behalf of the government or the country, in the face of some harsh and difficult questions raised by journalists or other diplomats. We will express our views and opinions on the standpoint of abiding by the principle of national interests, and always maintain the image of the country. In the process of verbal communication, sometimes the use of a determiner for the needs of communication can enhance the understanding of both parties.

Example 20:

Q: Recently, the Libyan anti-government organization established the "excessive national committee". Does China consider recognizing its status?

A: We are very concerned about the situation in Libya and hope that Libya and normal order can be restored in Libya as soon as possible. We hope relevant parties can resolve the current crisis through dialogue and other peaceful means.

Regarding the reporter's question, the spokesperson of the Ministry of Foreign Affairs did not clearly answer. We expressed our concern about the situation in Libya with great concern and determiners. We hope that social stability and normal order can be restored to Libya as soon as possible and relevant parties can resolve the current crisis through dialogue and other peaceful means. Although this kind of information is not what journalists want to obtain, from the perspective of national interests, such answers not only protect the interests and sovereign rights of the Libyan government, but also protect the interests of all parties.

3.3.3 Humor Principle

Humor is "the speech behavior and expression that people can make people laugh in the process of verbal communication. Because people's communicative activities mainly depend on context, humor is mostly generated in context." The use of speech is inseparable from context. Humor is inseparable from context. Context is the place where both parties understand and express their discourse. If we have a full understanding and understanding of the context and can use it skillfully, we can achieve communication success.

In verbal communication, in order for communication to proceed smoothly, both parties need to follow certain principles of cooperation. Only in this way can we ensure the smooth progress of the conversation. Cooperative principles include: quantity criteria, relationship criteria, quality criteria, and methodological

guidelines. When a talker uses a subtle and euphemistic expression to convey his or her own communication intentions, he or she will deliberately violate one or more of these criteria. The talker's discourse may have some extraneous meaning or extra-string sound. If the listener can correctly understand the profound connotation hidden in the speaker's discourse according to a certain context, then the purpose of communication is achieved; if the listener only literally understands the surface meaning of the spoken language, the true meaning of the speaker is misunderstood. Intention, then in the verbal communication will lead to the emergence of humor. Therefore, humor is caused by the communicator's violation of the principle of cooperation in communication. The speaker does not know that his own words have not followed certain cooperative principles, nor have they met the consequences, which has caused the misunderstanding of the hearers or the misinterpretation of the readers, and thus produced humorous effects.

Example 21. During Premier Zhu Rongji's visit to the United States, the so-called Chinese theft of US nuclear technology was in full swing. At a press conference, someone raised this question. Premier Zhu replied: "The mayor of Los Angeles once asked me how to celebrate this year's 50th anniversary (National Day). I replied that China will exhibit the most modern Chinese-made Weapons, not stolen from the United States. The mayor's wife immediately suggested that you should show China-made weapons on the weapons." President and President Clinton, who accompanied them, were laughed at by this answer.

Premier Zhu Rongji's question to reporters did not answer positively. Instead, he used determiners to lead us to show the most modern weapons we made in China during the National Day, instead of stealing them from the United States. Such a humorous answer not only gave a powerful rebuttal and criticism to the absurd nonsense of the so-called theft of US nuclear weapons technology, but also showed the United States the strength of our military defense. A pun is very aggressive.

Conclusion

When analyzing the types and functions of determiners and the usage strategies of determiners, the modifier role is also closely followed. In diplomatic occasions, achieving successful communication has a certain effect, but in some sense, it also has some negative effects. If diplomatist misemploy, it will lead to misunderstanding, ambiguity, and even unnecessary trouble or loss. Therefore, in the actual communication, individuals must analyze the determiner in the diplomatic rhetoric, use it flexibly, make overall considerations, and pay attention to the comprehensive effect.

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